

Analysis

Informing groundwater policies in semi-arid agricultural production regions under stochastic climate scenario impacts

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ABSTRACT

Region-specific groundwater policies are required to regulate groundwater extraction for agricultural irrigation and reduce climate change adaptation externalities. We examine the semi-arid Seewinkel region in Austria and explore interactions between climatic, agronomic, hydrological, and socio-economic conditions and processes to provide policy advice. The assessment is conducted with a spatially explicit integrated modeling framework to analyze impacts on land and irrigation water use, land management, and net benefits of agricultural production. The model results show that with imposed groundwater restrictions for irrigation, land use shifts from irrigated vineyards to mostly rainfed cropland with declining regional net benefits of agricultural production. The direction of change is similar for a DRY, SIMILAR, and WET climate scenario, while the magnitude differs. We estimate that an increase of the marginal value of groundwater extraction for irrigation by 0.1 €/m³ results in an average decrease in groundwater extraction volumes by 17.2 Mm³ in DRY, 6.3 Mm³ in SIMILAR, and 6.4 Mm³ in WET. Furthermore, regional net benefits of agricultural production decrease by 3.4 M€ in DRY and SIMILAR, and by 1.6 M€ in WET, on average. Our assessment highlights that efficient groundwater policies can help to sustain groundwater availability in semi-arid regions, particularly under climate change.

1. Introduction

1.1. Interactions between agriculture and groundwater use

Globally, the agricultural sector is the largest water user (Döll 2009). About 70% of groundwater extractions support agricultural production systems (Margat and van der Gun 2013), which represent more than 40% of the total irrigation water (Döll et al. 2012). These percentages are even higher in semi-arid regions, where groundwater use for irrigation has increased in relevance over the last decades (Garrido et al. 2006; Siebert et al. 2010). Agriculture in semi-arid regions is thus vulnerable to water scarcities and groundwater depletion (Fraser et al. 2013). At the same time, it contributes to groundwater externalities (Karner et al. 2019; Pfeiffer and Lin 2012) and gives rise to inter-sectoral competition for water use (Flörke et al. 2018) and social conflicts (Varela-Ortega et al. 2011). For instance, Tracy et al. (2019) pointed out that decreasing groundwater levels increase costs for groundwater pumping and decrease productivity of groundwater wells. It may further necessitate drilling of new wells and, thus, affect farmers' net benefits. Pinke et al. (2020) found only weak relationships between wheat yield

and groundwater levels but showed that maize yield variability in rainfed agriculture had increased with falling groundwater levels. Furthermore, groundwater use for irrigation may have spatial externalities (such that a holder of groundwater rights can only partly capture the water beneath his or her land, Pfeiffer and Lin 2012) and environmental externalities (such as habitat and biodiversity loss, Krachler et al. 2012).

Climate change, which manifests in changes of mean climate parameters and of climate extremes, may reinforce or alleviate tensions between competing demands for groundwater and land. If farmers adapt in order to reduce climate change-related risks or utilize emerging opportunities for their farms, intended and unintended external effects may arise, i.e., climate change adaptation externalities (Mitter et al. 2018; Tompkins and Eakin 2012). For instance, Taylor et al. (2013) highlighted the increasing relevance of groundwater-fed irrigation for global food security under likely increasing climate extremes and pointed to related challenges for sustaining continuous drinking water supply. For a case study region in Germany, Kreins et al. (2015) simulated a 20fold increase in total irrigation demand, which resulted in a calculated tenfold increase of the share of irrigation water from

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groundwater to more than 30% under a long-term climate change scenario. Given the drastic increase in irrigation water demand, they concluded that groundwater management will gain in relevance in the future to coordinate water supply and demand.

1.2. Agricultural groundwater management

The likely increasing pressure on groundwater resources from agriculture under climate change and the increasing knowledge on potential consequences of groundwater depletion in semi-arid regions has encouraged the development of engineering, agricultural land use and management, and policy instruments to reduce negative externalities from climate change adaptation on groundwater resources (Tracy et al. 2019). Engineering refers to scheduling of groundwater pumping operations and to physical measures. The latter aim to regain a hydrologic balance in an aquifer, mostly known as managed aquifer recharge or groundwater banking (Scanlon et al. 2012). Land use and management address farmers' selection of drought-tolerant crops and varieties, the application of advanced irrigation technology combined with improved understanding of plant water demand, and adequate soil management to enhance the soil water holding capacity.

Policies comprise regulatory and market-based instruments, which are typically implemented and monitored by federal or regional public authorities. Direct regulation prescribes, limits or forbids certain inputs (e.g., pumping limits for groundwater) or technologies (e.g., efficient irrigation, sensor-based or weather observation technologies) for agricultural production, or it specifies the timing or location of certain activities such as groundwater-fed irrigation during the growing season. Direct regulation has proven effective if few agents are engaged or a low number of technologies are in use (Tol 2019). Market-based instruments – very well summarized by Koundouri (2004) and Rey et al. (2019) – include volumetric taxes or taxes on changes in the groundwater level, volume-based fixed or flexible quotas based on the state of the groundwater, and investment subsidies, low-interest loans or financial incentives to increase environmental services or reduce groundwater extraction (e.g., premium to reduce irrigation, buyback of pumping permits for groundwater, conversion of irrigated into rainfed production systems). Voluntary agreements can supplement direct regulations and market-based instruments. They rely on non-monetary incentives, such as moral suasion, to solve water allocation problems and have been implemented in various regions (e.g., Rey et al. 2017).

Empirical analyses of groundwater policies allow the conclusion that their effectiveness and efficiency depends (inter alia) on spatial and temporal flexibility, and on integrating the affected economic agents. For instance, Graveline (2019) found that combining a flexible tax with a flexible quota system can improve the groundwater state in an irrigated agricultural region. She suggested a stepwise introduction and the adjustment of market-based instruments to regional hydrological and economic specificities. Similarly, Varela-Ortega et al. (2011) concluded that well-balanced region-specific policies which consider agricultural and water objectives are of major relevance to successfully manage groundwater resources. These findings call for the development of methodological advancements and systematic analyses in order to support the design of region-specific policies for managing groundwater extractions and externalities, with a particular focus on agricultural land use and regional net benefits of agricultural production.

1.3. Policy analyses on the interactions between agriculture and groundwater use

Cross-sectoral policy analyses that address the interactions between land and water resources are still limited despite of the growing importance of nexus approaches and economic and environmental policy coordination (Albrecht et al. 2018). Economic models have been employed to better understand effects of different groundwater policies on resource allocation in agricultural production (Calzadilla et al. 2014).

In this context, Graveline (2016), Kahil et al. (2015) and Koundouri (2004) proposed two major approaches, i.e., econometric models, which base their estimations on observed data, and mathematical programming models, which can be defined as a set of equations including an objective function and constraints. It has been noted that econometric models are limited to the spectrum of conditions used for their development and may not be valid for policy evaluations that are out of the range of past experience (Lichtenberg et al. 2010; Mitter et al., 2015). Mathematical programming models have been criticized such that plant growth and hydrology may not be sufficiently addressed in pre-specified functions (Koundouri 2004).

Thus, recent studies have used hydro-economic modeling to identify efficient groundwater policies (Harou et al. 2009). For instance, Varela-Ortega et al. (2011) integrated an economic optimization model, a hydrological model and climate scenarios to analyze the effects of various agricultural and water policies on, e.g., farm income, water consumption, water costs, water productivity, and public expenditure. Similarly, Graveline (2019) coupled a calibrated economic model of agricultural supply with a semi-distributed calibrated hydrogeological model to analyze the cost-effectiveness of alternative policy instruments at regional level considering climate change scenarios. Robert et al. (2018) used stochastic dynamic programming to model farmers' crop and water management decisions under climate change and water policy scenarios. Kahil et al. (2015) applied discrete stochastic programming to evaluate market-based policy instruments for irrigated agriculture, whereby climate change scenarios and agricultural adaptation were considered.

1.4. Knowledge gaps and research objectives

The need to improve the understanding of interactions between bio-physical processes and socio-economic systems under changing climate conditions has been highlighted in the context of hydro-economic models (Graveline 2016; Taylor et al. 2013). However, the integration of bio-physical process models in groundwater policy analyses is still rare, and changes in bio-physical constraints for land use and land management are often disregarded though critical for understanding policy implications (Deines et al. 2020). Furthermore, spatially explicit modeling of land and water use needs to be advanced because of its relevance for accurately reflecting heterogeneity in resources and agricultural water management, for capturing interactions across space and time and, hence, for avoiding misleading policy recommendations (Brozović et al. 2010). Considering stochastic climate scenarios has been recommended for analyzing vulnerable and sensitive groundwater bodies in semi-arid regions (Holman et al. 2009) and for improving agricultural adaptation decisions (Karner et al. 2019; Mitter and Schmid 2019). However, little is known about the combined impact of stochastic climate scenarios and groundwater policies on land and water use. Understanding these impacts and interactions has been identified as particularly important at regional level because of spatial heterogeneities (Cai et al. 2015) and related differences in the suitability of land and technologies to agricultural production systems (Deines et al. 2020; Tracy et al. 2019). For climate extremes such as droughts, Hagenlocher et al. (2019) identified the assessment of scenarios for coherent policy development as a further knowledge gap. This includes the need for additional research on balancing sectoral interests, such as crop yields, and groundwater conservation, as concluded by Xiang et al. (2020).

The design and implementation of balanced, region-specific policies is a major task to improve agricultural groundwater management and reduce conflicts about freshwater resources. We aim to model interdependencies between climatic, agronomic, hydrological, and socio-economic conditions and processes, and to provide scientifically sound information for policy and decision making. Hence, we develop a spatially explicit, integrated modeling framework to model interactions in the soil-water-plant-atmosphere system and to identify efficient land and water use strategies under stochastic climate scenarios and groundwater policies. The integrated modeling framework is applied in

a semi-arid region in East Austria, the Seewinkel. In particular, we are interested in how regional groundwater extraction volumes, land and irrigation water use, land management, and net benefits of agricultural production change under stochastic climate scenarios and imposed restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation.

The article is structured as follows. In section 2, we shortly describe the models and how they are coupled in the integrated modeling framework. In section 3, we present results from the application of the integrated modeling framework for the Seewinkel region. In section 4, we discuss the model results and the applied methodological approach, and in section 5, we draw conclusions.

2. Integrated modeling framework

A spatially explicit integrated modeling framework has been developed for the Seewinkel region at 500 m grid resolution. It consists of stochastic climate scenarios (Strauss et al. 2013b), the crop rotation model CropRota (Schönhart et al. 2011), the bio-physical process model EPIC (Environmental Policy Integrated Climate; Williams 1995), and the non-linear bottom-up economic land use optimization model BiomAT (Karner et al. 2019). The integrated modeling framework is illustrated in Fig. 1. Individual models as well as model linkages are explained in the following sub-sections.

2.1. Case study region Seewinkel

The semi-arid Seewinkel region of about 45,100 ha is located in the pannonian climate zone in eastern Austria. Mean annual temperature is around 10 °C and mean annual precipitation is around 650 mm (Chimani et al. 2016). The agricultural sector is currently dominating land and groundwater use. However, demand from other sectors including tourism, nature conservation, settlements, and infrastructure has increased over the last decades. At present, about 56% of the total area (25,200 ha) are used for crop cultivation, about 6% (2650 ha) for grassland, and about 10% (4500 ha) for vineyards. Irrigation water is extracted from groundwater and mostly applied with sprinklers on

cropland (e.g., for sugar beet, potatoes, maize, cereals, soybean, and sunflower) and with drip irrigation systems in vineyards (Reisner 2014). The Seewinkel region is defined along an individual groundwater body built in the Tertiary. The Lake Neusiedl (Neusiedler See) forms the western border. It is the largest endorheic lake of Central Europe and is part of the transboundary national park Neusiedler See-Seewinkel. The national park is characterized by a decreasing number of saline lakes that form unique biotopes for rare species (Krachler et al. 2012). These lakes require a minimum groundwater level for the capillary uptake of salts from the soil, which increases the relevance of groundwater management in the region.

Groundwater extraction is currently regulated via a ‘regional consensus’. Farmers in the region have formed water cooperatives and legally binding decisions regulate the annual volume of water (m³/a), the maximum productivity (l/s), and the irrigation months for each cooperative. The respective levels and months have been defined based on expected ten-year-averages, whereby regional climate conditions, regional groundwater recharge, likely future crop rotations, and a buffer amount of 20% are considered. The groundwater level is monitored at measurement sites across the region. If it fell below a defined value, the farmers would be asked to limit irrigation (Personal information, 2019). Furthermore, regional actors agree on the vital necessity of cross-sectoral groundwater management. Potential though controversially discussed policies and measures are volumetric taxes, external water supply from the Hungarian Danube, backwater measures, and managed infiltration of treated waste water (Kropf et al. 2020).

2.2. Statistical climate model for Austria

Three stochastic climate scenarios – DRY, SIMILAR, and WET – are derived from a statistical climate model for Austria (Strauss et al. 2013a, 2013b). The model is based on reported daily weather station data from across Austria for the years 1975 to 2007. It combines a dry day index with a block bootstrapping procedure to provide spatially explicit scenarios for a future period of 31 years (2010–2040). The dry day index reflects the share of the Austrian territory that is dry (i.e., without

Fig. 1. Schematic overview on the integrated modeling framework.

precipitation) on a random day. It ranges between zero and one and decreases if rain or snow is reported in large areas. For the block bootstrapping procedure, four blocks of eight or seven consecutive days are built for individual months. For each historical block, the dry day index is calculated in order to identify 'dry' and 'wet' blocks. Samples are drawn from the historical blocks of a defined month. The sampling procedure is rerun 30 times to obtain stochastic climate scenarios. A distribution of daily weather data is derived from the statistical climate model for maximum and minimum temperature, precipitation, solar radiation, relative humidity and wind speed at 1 km grid resolution and a period of 31 years.

Three stochastic climate scenarios are considered because changes in precipitation sums are subject to high uncertainties in the region (Chimani et al. 2016). The three stochastic climate scenarios differ in the projected share of dry days and its spatial extents. In SIMILAR, the distribution of the dry day index is similar to the past and can be interpreted as a projection of reported dry and wet spells. In DRY, the share of dry days is higher than in the past because 'dry blocks' are chosen more frequently in the sampling procedure. Likewise, in WET, the share of wet days is higher than in the past because 'wet blocks' are chosen more frequently. DRY and WET represent an increase in multi-seasonal dry and wet spells, respectively. Figs. A.1 and A.2 (in the Appendix) show differences in mean annual precipitation sums and mean annual temperature between the three climate scenarios for the Seewinkel region, and Fig. 2 depicts the variation in monthly precipitation through the annual cycle. A major advantage of the statistical climate model is the spatio-temporal and physical consistency of the six weather parameters. This is reflected by e.g., significant temperature increases in DRY, compared to SIMILAR (Strauss et al., 2013). However, it should be noted that precipitation regimes are similar due to the flat topography of the Seewinkel region located in the Pannonian Plain. The modeled daily weather data are input to the bio-physical process model EPIC.

2.3. Crop rotation model CropRota

The crop rotation model CropRota is applied to obtain typical crop rotations for each municipality in the Seewinkel region as well as their relative cropland shares (Schönhart et al. 2011). CropRota uses reported land use data from the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) and an expert-based agronomic score matrix that values pre-crop

and main-crop sequences of 23 crops and fallow by its agronomic suitability. CropRota is a linear programming model maximizing the total value of agronomic suitability over all crop rotations at municipality level, subject to reported crop shares and crop rotation restrictions. Considering crop rotations acknowledges that average annual irrigation water use differs between crops with effects on the water balance (see Reisner (2014) for estimates of average annual irrigation water use for typical crops in the Seewinkel region). The crop rotations are modeled over the 31-year period and consist of one to six crops in a sequence. A sequence of one crop refers to a monoculture (e.g., maize), and a sequence with two or more crops refers to the situation that two or more crops are alternated (e.g., maize and soybean) within the 31-year period. The crop rotations are proportionally and spatially assigned to 500 m grid cells and feed into the bio-physical process model EPIC.

2.4. Bio-physical process model EPIC

The bio-physical process model EPIC (Williams 1995) simulates interactions in the soil-water-plant-atmosphere system at a daily time step and has been validated extensively for global (e.g., Folberth et al. 2019), European (e.g., Balković et al. 2013), national and regional applications (e.g., Mitter et al. 2015a; Mitter and Schmid 2019; Schmid 2006; Stürmer et al. 2013). The validated EPIC model for Austria is used to simulate annual dry matter yields and environmental outcomes including components of the water balance, e.g., rainfall, evapotranspiration, irrigation water use, surface runoff, subsurface flow, and percolation. The simulations are conducted for various land and water management practices and the three stochastic climate scenarios DRY, SIMILAR, and WET at a 500 m grid resolution. Five land use classes including cropland, intensive grassland, extensive grassland, vineyards, and other land are modeled with EPIC, whereby other land is simulated as rangeland without harvesting and management. A 31-year period until 2040 is simulated for each land use class and respective land and water management practices using the 30 bootstrapped realizations of each of the three climate scenarios. The Penman-Monteith equation is chosen to calculate potential evapotranspiration (Monteith 1965; Monteith and Moss 1977; Stockle et al. 1992), which allows to consider the CO₂ fertilization effect.

Major inputs required in EPIC are daily weather data, soil and topographic data, and data on land and water management practices.

Fig. 2. Boxplots with 30 realizations of monthly precipitation sums (in mm) in the Seewinkel region for a future period of 31 years and the three climate scenarios. Note: Outliers are not shown.

Daily weather data are taken from the statistical climate model (sub-section 2.2), soil data are derived from the Austrian Soil Map 1:25,000 (Soil Map, 2011), and slope and elevation are extracted from a digital elevation model for Austria. The land and water management practices consider type and timing of tillage operations, crop rotations, fertilizer application levels, irrigation technology and intensity, and mowing frequencies on grasslands. Dates of planting, fertilizer and irrigation applications, tillage operation, and harvesting vary annually because they are automatically adjusted in EPIC based on heat unit accumulation. Potential heat unit requirements by crop are kept constant for the 31-year-simulation period. Crop rotations are derived with CropRota and cover a bandwidth of historically cultivated crops (sub-section 2.3). Up to three fertilizer application levels (high, moderate, low) are simulated for rainfed and irrigated cropland to represent legal standards and policy guidelines (e.g., BMLFUW 2012, 2006). Crop-specific nitrogen inputs are given in Table A.1 (in the Appendix) by fertilizer application level. Nitrogen inputs are 120 kg/ha on intensive grassland (irrigated and rainfed), 60 and 30 kg/ha on extensive grassland (rainfed), and 70 and 50 kg/ha on irrigated vineyards.

Sprinkler irrigation is simulated on cropland and intensive grassland, and drip irrigation is simulated for vineyards because these are the dominant irrigation technologies in the case study region (Reisner 2014). Groundwater is the only source of irrigation water, which is the current regional practice (Personal information, 2019). Four irrigation intensities are studied for cropland (i.e., airr, air2, rirr, rir2), two for vineyards (i.e., aird, rird), and one irrigation intensity is considered for intensive grassland (i.e., airr). The irrigation intensities differ by the allowed maximum annual irrigation volume and the water stress factor to trigger irrigation, which are defined in Table A.2. Irrigation is not considered for extensive grassland and other land because additional costs can hardly be compensated (wpa Beratende Ingenieure, 2011). Information from regional water cooperatives has guided the assumptions on maxima of annual irrigation water use (Reisner 2014). With respect to mowing frequencies, three cuts are assumed on intensive grassland and one cut on extensive grassland.

2.5. Gross margin calculation

Annual gross margins are calculated for arable crops, permanent grass, and wine by 500 m grid cell as well as by land and water management practices, and 30 bootstrapped realization of the three stochastic climate scenarios DRY, SIMILAR, and WET. The calculations are based on the yields, fertilization rates, and irrigation water demands simulated with EPIC and respective commodity prices from Statistics Austria averaged over the period 2015–2017. Variable production costs for land and water management practices (including labor) as well as annualized capital costs for irrigation equipment are taken from the Bundesanstalt für Agrarwirtschaft (2018) and Heumesser et al. (2012). The direct price for irrigation water is zero, which is conform to current Austrian water law (Wasserrechtsgesetz, 1959).

Agricultural policy premiums reflect current conditions and comprise of a uniform decoupled payment of 283 €/ha for cropland, intensive grassland, and vineyards and of 57 €/ha for extensive grassland and other land. Agri-environmental payments for reduced and low fertilizer application are 50 and 115 €/ha, respectively. Commodity prices, variable production costs, annualized capital costs for irrigation equipment, and policy premiums are kept constant over time in order to separate effects from groundwater restrictions and climate change from future market and agricultural policy developments. Gross margins are input to the bottom-up economic land and water use optimization model BiomAT.

2.6. Non-linear bottom-up economic land and water use optimization model BiomAT

BiomAT is a spatially explicit bottom-up economic land and water

use optimization model for Austria (Mitter et al. 2015b; Stürmer et al. 2013). A non-linear objective function has been introduced using a Positive Mathematical Programming approach (PMP; Howitt 1995) in order to calibrate the model to reported land use data from the past (Feusthuber et al. 2017; Karner et al. 2019). The model has been extended by a regional water balance with monthly dynamics of water supply, demand and storage. Hence, water supply and demand are not only dependent on hydrological components (e.g., rainfall, evapotranspiration, percolation, irrigation), but also on land use and management choices and the possibility of groundwater extraction for irrigation. Hence, irrigation water is sourced by percolation water and groundwater. Percolation water is available without resource use costs but pumping costs and groundwater with resource use costs and pumping costs. The model has been validated against information on irrigation water demand from regional water cooperatives (Reisner et al. 2014; Karner et al. 2019). EPIC outputs on monthly irrigation water use and percolation are used to model the regional water balance in BiomAT. Lateral inflow and outflow between grid cells are considered in BiomAT in order to represent the Seewinkel region as an individual groundwater body. Land use change (e.g. conversion of grassland to cropland) is allowed in all grid cells.

The PMP version of BiomAT maximizes regional net benefits of agricultural production subject to spatial land endowments and the regional water balance. It uses a non-linear objective function comprising of the gross margins and the marginal values of the dual variables η for land use (in €/ha) and λ for groundwater extraction for irrigation (in €/m³, eq. 1).

$$\max NB = \sum_{i,j,k} GM_{i,j,k} x_{i,j,k} - \lambda \sum_{i,m} gwex_{i,m} - \begin{cases} \sum_{i,j} \frac{\eta_{i,j} \tilde{x}_{i,j}^\alpha}{\alpha (x_{i,j}^0)^{\alpha-1}} & | x_{i,j}^0 > 0 \\ \sum_{i,j} \eta_{i,j} \tilde{x}_{i,j} & | x_{i,j}^0 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In the objective function, *GM* refers to gross margins (in €/ha), and *x* is land use (in ha). The index *i* denotes the grid cell ($I = 1804$), *j* the land use class, with $J = 5$ (cropland, intensive and extensive grassland, vineyards, and other land), and *k* represents land and water management practices, with $K = 14$ (including alternative crop rotations, fertilizer application levels, irrigation intensities, and mowing frequencies). Note, land use change is not restricted, i.e., conversion between cropland, grassland, and vineyards is entirely flexible. The first term of the objective function sums the product of gross margins and land use for each grid cell, land use class, and management practice. The second term represents the costs of groundwater extraction (in €) with λ in €/m³ and the volume of groundwater extraction (*gwex*) in m³, whereby months are indexed by *m*, with $M = 12$. The third term represents the PMP cost function. The product of the marginal value of η and land use \tilde{x} to the power of the PMP coefficient α is divided by reported land use from the past x^0 and summed over grid cell *i* and land use class *j*. The PMP coefficient is assumed to be two representing a quadratic cost function, which is usually used if further information is not available (see e.g., Howitt 1995). The quadratic part of the cost function is used if reported land use is greater than zero, otherwise the linear part is used in the model.

The equality constraints (eqs. 2 and 3) ensure that land use summed over land and water management practices equals total land endowment of 25 ha in each grid cell *i*.

$$\sum_j \tilde{x}_{i,j} = 25 \forall i \quad (2)$$

$$\tilde{x}_{i,j} = \sum_k x_{i,j,k} \forall i, j \quad (3)$$

The regional water balance is given in eq. 4.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & - \sum_{j,k} PRK_{i,j,k,m} x_{i,j,k} - \sum_{\tilde{i}} inf_{i,\tilde{i},m} - gwex_{i,m} - wl_{i,m-1} \\
 & + \sum_{\tilde{i}} outf_{i,\tilde{i},m} + \sum_{j,k} IRGA_{i,j,k,m} x_{i,j,k} + wl_{i,m} \leq 0 \forall i, m
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

It balances monthly percolation (PRK) in grid cell i , land use class j and management practice k , monthly inflow (inf) from neighboring grids \tilde{i} to grid i , and monthly groundwater extraction (gwex) in grid i with monthly irrigation (IRGA) in grid i , land use class j , management practice k as well as monthly water outflow (outf) from grid i to neighboring grids \tilde{i} (all in m^3). The water balance equation also allows water storage from the previous month ($wl_{i,m-1}$) and the current month ($wl_{i,m}$) in each grid cell i . It should be noted that percolation water is available for irrigation at no resource use costs, but pumping costs, while λ reflects the resource use price for groundwater extraction.

The calibration constraints (eqs. 5 and 6) are only used in the linear maximization problem to derive the marginal values of the dual variables η and λ .

$$\sum_k x_{i,j,k} = x_{i,j}^0 \forall i, j \tag{5}$$

$$\sum_{i,m} gwex_{i,m} = 0 \tag{6}$$

Conceptually, the marginal values of the dual variables are the sensitivity of the objective function value to the respective constraint. Modeled land use is forced to perfectly replicate reported land use from the past x^0 (eq. 5) and groundwater extraction is calibrated to zero (eq. 6). Note, only the amount of percolation water can be used for irrigation in the calibration.

λ represents the marginal value of groundwater extraction for irrigation in the Seewinkel region. In the analysis, eight levels of λ are used ranging from 0 to 0.7 €/m³ to compute corresponding groundwater extraction volumes as well as effects on land and irrigation water use, land management, and net benefits of agricultural production for the Seewinkel region. The range of λ captures the marginal values of restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation. The model results reveal the necessary changes in land and water use as well as the impacts on regional net benefits of agricultural production. Hence, a λ of 0 €/m³ indicates a situation without any restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation. Increasing levels of λ indicate an increasing groundwater use price imposed by restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation by policies. A groundwater use price of 0.7 €/m³ reflects a situation, where groundwater extraction for irrigation is almost zero in each realization of the three stochastic climate scenarios (see sub-section 3.1). The relationship between λ (€/m³) and the groundwater extraction volumes (m^3) can inform the design of efficient groundwater regulations or market-based instruments for irrigation management in the region. BiomAT was solved for each of the eight λ levels as well as for each of the 30 bootstrapped realizations of the three stochastic climate scenarios DRY, SIMILAR, and WET.

Table 1

Water use in the Seewinkel region. Mean annual levels (in Mm³) and coefficients of variation (in brackets) for groundwater extraction volumes (gwex) and regional irrigation water use (irga) by λ levels (€/m³) and the three stochastic climate scenarios.

Climate scenario	DRY			SIMILAR			WET					
	λ	gwex	irga	gwex	irga	gwex	irga	gwex	irga			
0.7	0.0	(NA)	8.4	(0.20)	0.0	(NA)	20.8	(0.14)	0.0	(NA)	41.1	(0.07)
0.6	0.3	(2.67)	8.7	(0.17)	0.0	(NA)	20.8	(0.14)	0.0	(NA)	41.1	(0.07)
0.5	2.1	(1.38)	10.5	(0.24)	3.1	(2.13)	23.8	(0.29)	3.3	(1.45)	44.3	(0.13)
0.4	10.5	(0.75)	19.0	(0.39)	19.2	(0.94)	38.7	(0.48)	11.7	(0.79)	52.5	(0.17)
0.3	33.4	(0.50)	41.8	(0.39)	44.4	(0.36)	64.5	(0.26)	20.7	(0.37)	61.5	(0.12)
0.2	66.7	(0.24)	75.0	(0.20)	61.7	(0.13)	81.7	(0.10)	26.5	(0.22)	67.4	(0.06)
0.1	93.3	(0.07)	101.9	(0.05)	74.6	(0.07)	95.1	(0.04)	32.1	(0.18)	73.4	(0.05)
0.0	108.9	(0.03)	117.8	(0.02)	86.1	(0.05)	107.1	(0.03)	42.9	(0.14)	84.9	(0.04)

3. Results

3.1. Impacts on groundwater extraction and irrigation water use

Model results from BiomAT for annual groundwater extraction volumes and irrigation water use are summarized in Table 1 for the Seewinkel region by λ levels and the three stochastic climate scenarios. The model results show that the mean groundwater extraction volume ranges between 108.9 Mm³ under DRY, 86.1 Mm³ under SIMILAR, and 42.9 Mm³ under WET climate conditions if groundwater extraction is not restricted and λ is zero. In contrast, groundwater extraction is, on average, zero in all climate scenarios if λ reaches 0.7 €/m³. Variability in groundwater extraction volumes differs with λ levels and climate scenarios. We calculate coefficients of variation (CV) to normalize the variabilities and find that it is highest at higher λ levels and under DRY climate conditions with average CVs amounting to 0.81 in DRY, 0.62 in SIMILAR, and 0.53 in WET.

Mean annual percolation in the region is simulated with about 8.5 Mm³ under DRY, 20.5 Mm³ under SIMILAR, and 41 Mm³ under WET climate conditions with low variability among the 30 bootstrapped realizations of the climate scenarios, i.e., CVs are between 0.2 in DRY, 0.14 in SIMILAR, and 0.07 in WET.

Mean annual irrigation water use in the Seewinkel region ranges between 8.4 and 117.8 Mm³ in DRY, between 20.8 and 107.1 Mm³ in SIMILAR, and up to 42.9 Mm³ in WET, with highest values without any groundwater policy restrictions, and lowest values with a λ of 0.7 €/m³. Mean irrigation water use continuously decreases with imposed restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation, whereby decreases are largest under DRY and smallest under WET climate conditions. Among the 30 bootstrapped realizations of the climate scenarios, variability of irrigation water use is on average highest in DRY (average CV of 0.21) and lowest in WET (average CV of 0.09).

Fig. 3 shows the relationship between groundwater extraction volumes and λ , whereby the 30 bootstrapped realizations for each climate scenario are considered in the boxplots. The relationship indicates how groundwater extraction for irrigation can be influenced by a market-based instrument, e.g., a volumetric tax, represented by λ . Groundwater extraction volumes decrease with increasing λ , whereby largest decreases are found under DRY and smallest decreases under WET climate conditions. We estimated the slope by using a linear regression model for the three stochastic climate scenarios. The results show that with an increase in λ by 0.1 €/m³ groundwater extraction volumes decrease on average by about 17.2 Mm³ in DRY, by about 6.3 Mm³ in SIMILAR, and by about 6.4 Mm³ in WET. If we assume a direct regulation, e.g., a pumping limit for groundwater, the respective value of λ can be taken from Fig. 3 as well. For instance, a groundwater extraction limit of 20 Mm³ would require, on average, a λ of about 0.3 €/m³ under WET climate conditions.

Spatial heterogeneity of average annual irrigation water use is shown in Fig. 4 for the three climate scenarios and three selected λ levels, i.e., 0.0, 0.2 and 0.5 €/m³. Without groundwater restrictions (a, b, c in Fig. 4), the entire Seewinkel region is irrigated, regardless of the climate

Fig. 3. Boxplots with 30 realizations of mean annual groundwater extraction volumes in Mm³ by λ levels (€/m³) and the three climate scenarios. Note: Eight levels of λ are shown ranging from 0 to 0.7 €/m³. However, the boxplots for the three climate scenarios are arranged around the exact levels for easier reading.

Fig. 4. Average annual irrigation water use in the Seewinkel region (in mm) by three λ levels, i.e., 0.0 €/m³ (first row), 0.2 €/m³ (second row) and 0.5 €/m³ (third row) and the three climate scenarios DRY (first column), SIMILAR (second column) and WET climate scenarios (third column). Note: Results from the BiomAT model were averaged over the 30 realizations for each climate scenario.

scenario. Large areas are irrigated with more than 200 mm on annual average, in particular under DRY and SIMILAR climate conditions. Irrigation water use below 200 mm are mostly found in the West (DRY, SIMILAR, WET) and in the South of the region (WET). In WET, mean annual irrigation is around 182 mm and hence lower than in DRY (251 mm) and SIMILAR (228 mm) while spatial variability of irrigation is highest in WET with a CV of 0.36 (0.23 in DRY and 0.27 in SIMILAR; Table A.3). The spatial patterns for irrigation water use are not only

driven by λ but also by land use and management.

With increasing λ levels, mean irrigation water use decreases across the region and some regions are not irrigated any more (e.g., in the West and the center of the region at a λ level of 0.5 €/m³ under DRY climate conditions). With a λ of 0.2 €/m³, mean irrigation is similar for the three climate scenarios whereas spatial variability, expressed by the CV, is highest in WET (0.53) and lowest in DRY (0.35). In WET and SIMILAR (λ of 0.2 €/m³), vineyards located in the center and the South-west (Fig. 6)

are largely irrigated. Spatial variability is increasing in DRY and SIMILAR and decreasing in WET with CV of 1.03 in DRY, 0.45 in SIMILAR, and 0.42 in WET at λ of 0.5 €/m³.

3.2. Impacts on land use

The regional shares of the five land use classes – cropland, intensive and extensive grassland, vineyards, and other land – are depicted in Fig. 5 by λ levels and the three climate scenarios. The average regional shares of cropland range between 28 and 53% under DRY, between 22 and 57% under SIMILAR, and between 21 and 45% under WET climate conditions, depending on the λ level. Cropland gains in importance with more restrictive policies on groundwater extraction for irrigation in all climate scenarios, as indicated by higher λ levels. Compared to SIMILAR, cropland decreases between 6 and 20% under WET climate conditions, whereas it increases between 5 and 27% under DRY climate conditions and a λ of up to 0.4 €/m³. Grassland is of minor importance for the Seewinkel region, regardless of the λ level. Average regional shares of intensive and extensive grassland are between 1 and 6% in DRY, between 4 and 9% in SIMILAR, and between 7 and 8% in WET. Extensive grassland increases with more restrictive policies on groundwater extraction for irrigation in all climate scenarios. For intensive grassland, the same applies under DRY and SIMILAR climate conditions. In WET, intensive grassland is highest at a λ level of 0.1 €/m³ and decreases continuously with higher λ levels.

Vineyards are the dominant land use class in the Seewinkel region if groundwater extraction for irrigation is not restricted, with average shares between 64% in DRY, 70% in SIMILAR, and 71% in WET. Vineyards decrease in all climate scenarios if groundwater extraction for irrigation is restricted, whereby decreases are highest under DRY and lowest under WET climate conditions. In DRY, the regional share of vineyards is about 6% with a λ level of 0.6 €/m³ and above and, thus, similar to the regional share of total grassland. In WET, vineyards are realized on about 42% of the area at a λ level of 0.6 €/m³ and above,

which is similar to the cropland share in this scenario. The regional share of other land amounts to 7% in DRY, 4% in SIMILAR, and 1% in WET, without any groundwater extraction restrictions for irrigation. Other land, which indicates that agricultural land is abandoned, increases in relevance with more restrictive policies on groundwater extraction for irrigation. At a λ level of 0.6 €/m³, its share is between 35% in DRY, 18% in SIMILAR, and 5% in WET.

Variabilities in regional land use resulting from the 30 realizations of the three stochastic climate scenarios are summarized in Table A.4 for the five land use classes. On average, variabilities (expressed by the CV) are highest for vineyards under DRY, for intensive grassland under SIMILAR, and for other land under WET climate conditions.

The spatial distribution of dominant land use is shown in Fig. 6 for the three climate scenarios and three selected λ levels, i.e., 0.0, 0.2 and 0.5 €/m³. Without restrictions on groundwater extractions for irrigation, the spatial pattern of land use is similar for the three climate scenarios, even if the extent of the land use classes differs. Cropland is mostly dominant in the North-west and spreads throughout the region with increasing λ levels, mostly at the cost of vineyards. Grassland and other land are predominate in the West, i.e., close to the national park in the three climate scenarios.

3.3. Impacts on land management

Management choices differ by land use class, λ level, and climate scenario. Fig. 7 shows average regional shares of optimal management on cropland by λ levels and the three climate scenarios. (Note that absolute levels (in ha) are given in Table A.5). A large share of cropland is irrigated if groundwater extraction for irrigation is not restricted and λ is zero. It ranges between almost 100% in DRY, 94% in SIMILAR, and 87% in WET, whereby high irrigation water use combined with high fertilizer application levels (air2) is the dominant management. The share of irrigated cropland decreases with more restrictive groundwater extraction policies for irrigation in all climate scenarios. For instance, it is

Fig. 5. Land use in the Seewinkel region by λ levels (€/m³) and the three stochastic climate scenarios. Note: Results from the BiomAT model were averaged over the 30 realizations of each climate scenario.

Fig. 6. Land use maps for the Seewinkel region by three λ levels, i.e., 0.0 €/m^3 (first row), 0.2 €/m^3 (second row) and 0.5 €/m^3 (third row) and the three climate scenarios DRY (first column), SIMILAR (second column) and WET climate scenarios (third column). Note: For each grid cell, the dominant land use class is shown. Results from the BiomAT model were averaged over the 30 realizations for each climate scenario.

Fig. 7. Land management on cropland by λ levels (€/m^3) and the three stochastic climate scenarios. Note: Results from the BiomAT model were averaged over the 30 realizations of each climate scenario. Combinations of fertilizer application levels and irrigation intensities are shown, i.e., high fertilizer application combined with very high irrigation (airr), high irrigation (air2) and no irrigation (high); moderate fertilizer application combined with moderate irrigation (rirr), low irrigation (rir2) and no irrigation (low); low fertilizer application combined with no irrigation (low).

between 23% in DRY, 14% in SIMILAR, and 7% in WET at a λ of 0.3 €/m³ with moderate and low irrigation water use combined with moderate fertilizer application levels being the relevant managements (rirr, rir2).

In DRY, low and moderate fertilization intensities gain in importance on rainfed cropland with increasing λ levels. Low fertilization intensity is found on about 6% of the cropland at a λ of 0.1 €/m³ and increases to about 85% of the cropland at a λ of 0.6 €/m³ and above. Moderate fertilization amounts to about 2% of total cropland at a λ of 0.1 €/m³ and to about 12% at a λ of 0.4 €/m³ or higher. High fertilization intensity (rainfed) is of minor importance in DRY, with a cropland share below 1% at all λ levels.

In SIMILAR, the share of rainfed cropland with low and moderate fertilization intensities increases with more restrictive groundwater extractions for irrigation. Low (moderate) fertilizer application rates are found on about 4% (1.5%) of the cropland without limitations for groundwater extraction and are above 50% (40%) at a λ level of 0.4 €/m³ or higher. High fertilization intensity without irrigation is of limited relevance with cropland shares between 0.5% without and about 2% with restrictions on groundwater extractions for irrigation.

In WET, the shares of rainfed cropping with moderate and high fertilization are larger than in SIMILAR and DRY. Moderate fertilization intensity is realized on 6% if groundwater extraction for irrigation is not restricted and takes about two thirds of the cropland at a λ level of 0.4 €/m³ or higher. High fertilization intensity takes between 2% of the cropland without restrictions and about 6% with restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation. Low fertilization intensity ranges between 5% without restrictions and up to one quarter of the cropland with restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation.

Variabilities in management choices resulting from the 30 realizations of the stochastic climate scenarios are summarized for cropland in Table A.6. They are, on average, higher for irrigated than for rainfed managements.

For permanent grassland, irrigation is only chosen on intensive grassland in DRY if groundwater extraction for irrigation is not limited. Nitrogen inputs of 60 kg/ha are dominant on extensive grassland with shares between 85 and 90% in DRY, between 86 and 100% in SIMILAR, and between 72 and 100% in WET, depending on the λ level. Low intensity (i.e., 30 kg N/ha) increases in importance with higher levels of λ in SIMILAR and WET.

For vineyards, the model results show that the entire area is irrigated in all three climate scenarios and regardless of the restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation. In DRY, high irrigation and fertilization intensity (aird) are chosen at all λ levels. In SIMILAR and WET, more than 90% of the area is managed with high irrigation and fertilization intensity. Moderate irrigation and fertilization intensity (rird) are more important at higher λ levels.

3.4. Impacts on regional net benefits of agricultural production

The model results for annual regional net benefits of agricultural production are summarized in Table 2 for eight λ levels and the three stochastic climate scenarios. Mean annual regional net benefits range

Table 2

Net benefits of agricultural production in the Seewinkel region. Mean annual levels (M€) and coefficients of variation (in brackets) by λ levels (€/m³) and the three stochastic climate scenarios.

λ	DRY		SIMILAR		WET	
0.7	7.6	(0.21)	20.2	(0.12)	38.1	(0.11)
0.6	7.6	(0.21)	20.2	(0.12)	38.1	(0.11)
0.5	7.7	(0.20)	20.3	(0.13)	38.2	(0.11)
0.4	8.3	(0.21)	21.2	(0.16)	39.0	(0.12)
0.3	10.4	(0.27)	24.5	(0.21)	40.6	(0.14)
0.2	15.4	(0.28)	29.8	(0.20)	43.0	(0.14)
0.1	23.5	(0.22)	36.6	(0.18)	45.9	(0.13)
0.0	33.7	(0.16)	44.8	(0.15)	49.7	(0.12)

between 7.6 and 33.7 M€ in DRY, 20.2 and 44.8 M€ in SIMILAR, and 38.1 and 49.7 M€ in WET. Regional net benefits are highest without any restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation, i.e., if λ is zero, in all climate scenarios. They decrease continuously with more restrictive groundwater extraction policies. Decreases are similar in DRY and SIMILAR and smallest in WET (Fig. 8). In order to evaluate this effect, we estimate changes in regional net benefits of agricultural production as a function of λ for each climate scenario, whereby model outputs for the 30 realizations of the stochastic climate scenarios are considered. The model results show that regional net benefits of agricultural production decrease by about 3.4 M€ in DRY and SIMILAR and by about 1.6 M€ in WET if λ increases by 0.1 €/m³. The boxplots in Fig. 8 also visualize the variability in regional net benefits of agricultural production among the 30 realizations of the stochastic climate scenarios. The variabilities, expressed by the CV, are highest in DRY and lowest in WET, regardless of the λ level. Within the climate scenarios, the variability is highest with a λ of 0.2 (DRY and WET) or 0.3 €/m³ (SIMILAR).

4. Discussion

4.1. Discussion of the model results

Our model results show economic, agronomic, and environmental impacts resulting from climate change scenarios and restrictions on groundwater extractions for irrigation in the Seewinkel region. Climate change adaptation in the agricultural sector can increase the pressure on already scarce resources including groundwater. Such climate change adaptation externalities call for the design and implementation of efficient policies for environmental and natural resource management. We find that with imposed restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation, groundwater extraction and irrigation volumes continuously decrease, dominant land use shifts from irrigated vineyards to mostly rainfed cropland, and regional net benefits of agricultural production decrease. A general decrease in irrigated agricultural land resulting from groundwater extraction policies is confirmed by previous studies (e.g., Varela-Ortega et al. 2011). Land use change was identified as a largely accepted climate change adaptation measure (Mitter et al. 2018), efficient conversions between land use classes were shown to depend on prevailing climate conditions in the future (Karner et al. 2019), and Deines et al. (2020) suggested that economic impacts of aquifer depletion may be underestimated if land use change is not adequately represented in assessments of agricultural water management.

The magnitude of economic, agronomic, and environmental impacts differs between the three stochastic climate scenarios, while the direction of change is similar. For instance, we find that with λ increasing by 0.1 €/m³, regional groundwater extraction volumes decrease, on average, by about 17.2 Mm³ under DRY and by about 6.4 Mm³ under WET climate conditions. Similarly, reductions in irrigation water use and vineyards are higher in DRY than in WET, and regional net benefits of agricultural production decrease, on average, by about 3.4 M€ in DRY and SIMILAR and by about 1.6 M€ in WET if λ increases by 0.1 €/m³. These values seem reasonable, if compared to results from other European case study regions. For instance, model results for an arid region in Spain and a future period of 18 years showed marginal values of irrigation water between 0.004 and 0.973 €/m³, depending on the policy option (Varela-Ortega et al. 2011). For French regions and considering climate change, Graveline (2019) found marginal values of water ranging between 0.008 and 0.38 €/m³ and decreases in farmers' net benefits between 33 and 86 €/ha, depending on the agricultural production region and the policy instrument. In a recent global study, D'Odorico et al. (2020) estimated the value of water, i.e. the maximum price farmers might accept to pay for irrigation water between 0.042 €/m³ (0.05 \$/m³) and 0.14 €/m (0.16 \$/m³), depending on the crop considered. However, Kropf et al. (2020) found that a further restriction of groundwater extraction for irrigation is contested among stakeholders in the Seewinkel region.

Fig. 8. Boxplots with 30 realizations of mean annual regional net benefits of agricultural production in M€ by λ levels (€/m³) and the three climate scenarios. Note: Eight levels of λ are shown ranging from 0 to 0.7 €/m³. However, the boxplots for the three climate scenarios are arranged around the exact levels for easier reading.

In our analysis, variabilities among the 30 bootstrapped realizations of the stochastic climate scenarios are higher in DRY than in WET for groundwater extraction volumes, irrigation water use, and regional net benefits of agricultural production. Variabilities are, on average, rather low, e.g., CVs range between 0.11 and 0.28 for regional net benefits. Similarly, Merrill and Guilfoos (2018) find that welfare gains from groundwater management increase only slightly when including stochasticity in rainfall in the estimation.

Regulatory and market-based policy instruments have been suggested for effectively managing groundwater resources and climate change adaptation externalities (see, e.g., Graveline 2019; Koundouri 2004; Rey et al. 2019). While we analyze interactions between regional restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation and land and water use to inform policy and decision making under climate change scenarios, we do not compare between or evaluate specific groundwater policies. However, previous analyses for arid and semi-arid regions found that private and social benefits are higher for water markets than for irrigation subsidies (Kahil et al. 2015), that quota-based policies may reduce groundwater use on farms but may be insufficient for aquifer recovery and stabilization (Varela-Ortega et al. 2011), and that a dual system that combines a flexible tax and a flexible quota system which is updated annually based on the groundwater state may outperform single instruments (Graveline 2019). Unintended side effects and implementation barriers are also decisive for the success of groundwater policy instruments (Rey et al. 2019). We analyze potential changes in land use, land management, and regional net benefits of agricultural production but disregard further environmental effects (e.g., on biodiversity or nitrate leaching) as well as farmers' acceptance of policy interventions and their preferences for specific instruments. Findings from Running et al. (2019) indicated that support for regional policies or agreements may be higher if land users trust in groundwater monitoring data and belief in the importance of groundwater protection; both aspects are currently not considered in our analysis.

4.2. Discussion of the integrated modeling framework

Our spatially explicit integrated modeling framework proved useful for assessing interactions between land and water use, and for informing the design of efficient groundwater extraction policy instruments under

uncertain future climate conditions for a semi-arid region in Austria. It considers a wide range of data that are decisive for land and water use, and how they may develop under stochastic climate scenarios and restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation by policies. Most important are soil, topographic, and climate data with a high spatial resolution, alternative land use and land and water management practices, and agricultural input and output prices. Integrating soil, land suitability, and stochastic climate data has been considered important for robustly estimating how climate change impacts land and water use (e.g., Deines et al. 2020; Holman et al. 2009) and for identifying efficient climate change adaptation measures (Karner et al. 2019).

However, some limitations remain, and our research could be extended in several ways. Further analyses on interactions between agricultural and water policies would be of interest for the case study region, for the scientific community, and for agricultural and water experts (Bazilian et al. 2011; Carvalho et al. 2019; Graveline 2016). Currently, we model agricultural policies in form of land use specific decoupled payments and agri-environmental payments for reductions in fertilizer application levels and consider groundwater extraction restrictions driven by regulatory or market based policy instruments. While combined effects on water quantity are considered, we disregard water quality in the analysis – an aspect particularly relevant in intensive agricultural production regions (BMNT 2018; Burri et al. 2019). We would, however, expect trade-offs with production-oriented and synergies with environmentally-oriented agricultural policies and water quality. We further assume that agricultural policy premiums will remain constant over time. This enables to show how climate change scenarios and restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation affect land and water use, land management, and regional net benefits of agricultural production and does not require projections on the development of the European and national agricultural policies over the next decades. An expected emphasis of European agricultural policy on climate and environment protection (European Commission 2018) would likely support less intensive management practices in our analysis with positive effects on water quality. Water quantity has already been addressed by agri-environmental measures in priority areas such as Italy, Spain, and the Netherlands (European Commission 2005; OECD 2015), but it has not yet been set as an explicit goal in Austria (Agrarmarkt Austria 2015). Similarly, Drought Management Plans (as

recommended by the Water Framework Directive; European Commission 2007; Global Water Partnership Central and Eastern Europe, 2015) have been established in some European regions, such as the Netherlands while in Austria, the scientific basis is currently developed and the link between agricultural and water policies could be further strengthened. Pulwarty and Sivakumar (2014) emphasized steady collaboration between concerned actors from multiple sectors and scales and clear leadership for improving policy coherence. In this context, urban planning policies are also of relevance because of the increasing land demand from, e.g., tourism, settlement, and infrastructure development. Non-agricultural land is currently considered as 'other land' in the integrated modeling framework and our results show an increase in 'other land' with increasing λ values and under DRY climate conditions. Soil sealing resulting from urbanization and its impacts on the regional water balance could be considered via scenarios in a next step. However, ongoing urbanization would likely result in reduced regional net benefits of agricultural production, whereby the magnitude of this change would depend on the spatial distribution of new settlements.

Mathematical programming models have been criticized for overspecialization and aggregation when applied at regional levels because they ignore resource and technical endowment of regional farms and regional farmers' management skills (Kahil et al. 2015). With BiomAT, we develop efficient land use as well as land and water management strategies by levels of restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation and stochastic climate scenarios at a spatial resolution of 500 m. Although the spatial resolution is high compared to other integrated assessments, it does not explicitly represent different farms or farming systems in the Seewinkel region nor how they may develop over time. However, Grafton et al. (2018) suggested to shift the focus from the field or farm to the watershed or basin scale to inform sustainable water management in agriculture. Furthermore, BiomAT was calibrated to reported land use data from the past using a PMP approach (Howitt 1995) and thus considers regional production conditions. Besides PMP, the representative farm approach (Day 1963) and convex combination (Önal and McCarl 1991) have been suggested for handling overspecialization and aggregation in mathematical programming models (Kahil et al. 2015).

Another aspect that deserves more attention is land use, and land and water management practices under changing climate and policy conditions. We consider land use change (e.g., extension of cropland over grassland), crop rotations, fertilizer application levels, irrigation intensities, and irrigation technologies in order to represent farmers' climate change adaptation possibilities (Mitter et al. 2019) and assume high flexibility in land use as well as land and water management in our analysis. However, land use change may be restricted because of agri-environmental guidelines or regulations at national or European level. This is currently the case for the extension of vineyards, which is strictly limited to 1% of the total area per year (European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, 2013). Hence, the model results likely overestimate wine-growing and related economic effects, particularly under WET and SIMILAR climate conditions, but they also indicate likely increasing pressures from land use on groundwater extraction under climate change. Furthermore, additional practices have been proposed for land and water management under changing climatic conditions including alternative tillage systems, crop varieties and crop stand management suited to soil and weather conditions, precision fertilization and irrigation, deficit irrigation, and fertigation (see, e.g., Iglesias and Garrote 2015). Considering such additional practices in the integrated modeling framework would increase the production possibility set of land use as well as land and water management choices with likely positive effects on regional net benefits of agricultural production and climate change adaptation externalities. However, data requirements and computational cost would increase as well. High flexibility in land and water management seems reasonable for crop choices, fertilizer application levels, and irrigation intensities. Land use change and investment in irrigation technology, however, require planning and

financial resources which may thus be introduced with delay (Mitter et al. 2018). We disregard transition phases for land use change but consider annualized investment costs for irrigation equipment in the gross margin calculation (Heumesser et al. 2012).

Finally, we have chosen three stochastic climate scenarios for our analysis. They have been derived from a statistical climate model for Austria and show a modest temperature increase of less than 1 °C until 2040, on average, for the 31-year period. By comparison, the ÖKS climate scenarios for Austria have been derived through interpolation and bias-correction of climate data from Regional Climate Models (RCMs) from the EURO-CORDEX initiative (Chimani et al. 2016) and suggest a regional temperature increase between 1.3 and 1.5 °C until 2050, on average. Larger temperature increases may, however, affect agricultural production and irrigation water demand, e.g. through an increase in heat stress and in evapotranspiration. Thus, the model results shall be interpreted in this context.

5. Conclusions

Climate change may increase competition for natural resources such as land and water and may thus jeopardize sustainable farming in semi-arid regions. The likely future increase in duration and intensity of climate extremes emphasizes the importance of explicitly considering groundwater levels in land use and land management planning. Groundwater policies may be implemented to handle or prevent land and water use conflicts, to decrease or reverse groundwater depletion, and to reduce climate change adaptation externalities. However, uncertainties in future climate conditions and limited understanding of interactions between land and water resources impairs evidence-based policy and decision making processes. Hence, we consider stochastic climate scenarios, soil-water-plant-atmosphere interactions, land use, land and water management practices, and agricultural and groundwater policies in our integrated modeling framework. Major model outputs are groundwater extraction volumes, land and irrigation water use, and land management under stochastic climate scenarios and restrictions on groundwater extraction for irrigation by policies. For the semi-arid Seewinkel region, the results indicate that more restrictive policies lead to lower groundwater extraction volumes from agriculture, to an increase in rainfed cropland, and to lower regional net benefits of agricultural production. The economic, agronomic, and environmental impacts are typically higher under DRY than under WET climate conditions. The results may be of interest for land users, water management authorities, and policy makers and could help to avoid freshwater limitations and decreasing groundwater tables in a heavily irrigated region with high ecological value. The application of the integrated modeling framework proved useful for the Seewinkel region and could be transferred to other regions, given plausible data are available. However, the design and enforcement of region-specific, efficient groundwater policies is a challenging task but may strengthen sustainable land and water management, in particular if model results are backed-up by regional experts' knowledge. Proactive management of regional land and water use may sustain groundwater availability under climate change, which is critical for the viability of farming and for maintaining ecosystems of high quality in the region. Finally, the integration and coherence of agricultural, climate, and water policies should be addressed in future research in order to establish successful policy interventions.

Declaration of Competing Interest

We declare no conflict of interest.

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Appendix A

Fig. A.1. Boxplots with 30 realizations of mean annual precipitation sums (mm) for a future period of 31 years for the Seewinkel region by stochastic climate scenarios (see Karner et al. 2019).

Fig. A.2. Boxplots with 30 realizations of mean annual temperature (°C) for a future period of 31 years for the Seewinkel region by stochastic climate scenarios.

Table A.1
Crop-specific nitrogen (N) input (kg/ha) by fertilization intensity.

#	Crop	High N input	Moderate N input	Low N input
1	Alfalfa	0	0	0
2	Alsike clover	40	20	0
3	Durum wheat	160	130	90
4	Faba bean	0	0	0
5	Fallow	0	0	0
6	Field pea	0	0	0
7	Grain maize	170	140	110
8	Grain sorghum	150	120	110
9	Oats	110	90	70
10	Potato	170	130	100
11	Red clover	0	0	0
12	Silage maize	175	150	120
13	Soybean	0	0	0
14	Spring barley	100	85	60
15	Sugar beet	140	110	100
16	Sunflower	80	60	50
17	Timothy	210	150	80
18	Triticale	130	110	80
19	Vegetables	100	80	60
20	Winter barley	150	120	80
21	Winter rape	175	140	110
23	Winter rye	120	100	70
24	Winter wheat	165	130	90

Table A.2
Specification of irrigation intensities for cropland, intensive grassland and vineyards.

	Max. annual irrigation volume (mm)	Water stress factor to trigger irrigation	Min. single application volume (mm)	Max. single application volume (mm)
Cropland				
airr	500	0.9	20	50
air2	300	0.8	20	50
rirr	200	0.8	20	50
rir2	100	0.7	20	50
Intensive grassland				
airr	300	0.8	20	50
Vineyards				
aird	300	0.8	1	5
rird	150	0.6	1	5

Notes: Four irrigation intensities are studied for cropland (i.e., airr, air2, rirr, rir2), two for vineyards (i.e., aird, rird), and one for intensive grassland (i.e., airr). The irrigation intensities differ by the allowed maximum annual irrigation volume and the water stress factor to trigger irrigation. A water stress factor to trigger irrigation of 0.9 means that 90% of the crop growth period is water stress free until the maximum annual irrigation volume is reached. Irrigation is not considered for extensive grassland and other land.

Table A.3
Irrigation water use in the Seewinkel region. Mean annual levels (mm) and standard deviations (in brackets) by three λ levels ($\text{€}/\text{m}^3$) and the three stochastic climate scenarios.

λ	DRY		SIMILAR		WET	
0.5	41	(42)	66	(29)	90	(37)
0.2	140	(49)	153	(68)	138	(73)
0.0	251	(57)	228	(62)	182	(65)

Table A.4
Land use in the Seewinkel region. Mean levels (in ha) and coefficients of variation (in brackets) for cropland, intensive and extensive grassland, vineyards, and other land by λ levels ($\text{€}/\text{m}^3$) and the three stochastic climate scenarios.

Land use class	Cropland		Intensive grassland		Extensive grassland		Vineyards		Other land	
λ DRY										
0.7	23,708	(0.03)	1397	(0.13)	1305	(0.03)	2634	(0.17)	16,055	(0.05)
0.6	23,680	(0.03)	1361	(0.15)	1303	(0.03)	2726	(0.15)	16,029	(0.05)
0.5	23,536	(0.02)	1226	(0.18)	1286	(0.05)	3203	(0.28)	15,848	(0.06)
0.4	22,899	(0.05)	790	(0.25)	1194	(0.11)	5324	(0.50)	14,892	(0.10)
0.3	19,902	(0.15)	415	(0.26)	899	(0.27)	12,110	(0.48)	11,774	(0.23)
0.2	15,142	(0.25)	262	(0.16)	569	(0.29)	21,455	(0.29)	7671	(0.31)
0.1	12,713	(0.23)	210	(0.16)	413	(0.12)	26,856	(0.14)	4908	(0.17)
0.0	12,710	(0.20)	172	(0.14)	300	(0.05)	28,804	(0.09)	3114	(0.05)
λ SIMILAR										
0.7	25,661	(0.03)	1813	(0.40)	2209	(0.11)	7294	(0.17)	8123	(0.18)

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Table A.4 (continued)

Land use class	Cropland		Intensive grassland		Extensive grassland		Vineyards		Other land	
0.6	25,661	(0.03)	1813	(0.40)	2209	(0.11)	7294	(0.17)	8123	(0.18)
0.5	25,153	(0.06)	1720	(0.45)	2160	(0.13)	8356	(0.33)	7712	(0.22)
0.4	21,793	(0.19)	1379	(0.41)	1802	(0.28)	13,878	(0.48)	6247	(0.37)
0.3	16,000	(0.27)	1179	(0.43)	1207	(0.35)	22,409	(0.27)	4304	(0.37)
0.2	11,780	(0.23)	1144	(0.41)	896	(0.21)	27,989	(0.12)	3291	(0.22)
0.1	10,075	(0.14)	1137	(0.40)	793	(0.06)	30,464	(0.05)	2632	(0.22)
0.0	10,021	(0.08)	974	(0.38)	704	(0.06)	31,566	(0.03)	1835	(0.23)
λ	WET									
0.7	20,459	(0.07)	2341	(0.18)	1061	(0.16)	18,887	(0.10)	2353	(0.25)
0.6	20,459	(0.07)	2341	(0.18)	1061	(0.16)	18,887	(0.10)	2353	(0.25)
0.5	19,297	(0.12)	2376	(0.16)	1004	(0.19)	20,237	(0.14)	2186	(0.25)
0.4	16,281	(0.22)	2508	(0.12)	878	(0.24)	23,652	(0.17)	1782	(0.25)
0.3	12,931	(0.22)	2694	(0.08)	777	(0.17)	27,319	(0.12)	1378	(0.23)
0.2	10,690	(0.15)	2893	(0.07)	735	(0.05)	29,736	(0.06)	1047	(0.22)
0.1	9516	(0.11)	2980	(0.06)	720	(0.04)	31,094	(0.04)	790	(0.23)
0.0	9423	(0.08)	2601	(0.07)	673	(0.04)	31,864	(0.03)	539	(0.22)

Table A.5

Land management on cropland in the Seewinkel region. Mean levels (in ha) for combinations of fertilizer application levels and irrigation intensities by λ levels (€/m³) and the three stochastic climate scenarios.

Management	high	moderate	low	airr	air2	rirr	rir2
λ	DRY						
0.7	131	2885	20,173	0	0	153	366
0.6	131	2882	20,126	0	0	154	386
0.5	131	2853	19,692	0	0	260	599
0.4	130	2627	17,602	0	0	1182	1358
0.3	129	1857	13,288	0	1	2720	1907
0.2	119	1036	6608	0	295	6398	687
0.1	102	192	788	320	3539	7588	183
0.0	0	0	0.3	3728	6126	2852	5
λ	SIMILAR						
0.7	429	10,747	13,540	0	0	333	611
0.6	429	10,747	13,540	0	0	333	611
0.5	419	10,537	13,209	0	0	345	643
0.4	384	8978	11,051	0	0	495	884
0.3	316	6134	7311	0	0	1098	1142
0.2	256	3654	4451	0	122	2345	952
0.1	221	1456	1519	6	1699	4793	380
0.0	44	138	410.7	1148	5641	2558	81
λ	WET						
0.7	1161	13,815	5134	0	0	69	279
0.6	1161	13,815	5134	0	0	69	279
0.5	1082	13,006	4831	0	0	69	309
0.4	925	10,834	4014	0	0	107	399
0.3	759	8257	3061	0	2	305	547
0.2	652	6354	2309	0	38	796	541
0.1	532	4191	1337	0	937	2230	289
0.0	187	600	438	1008	4336	2670	184

Note: Combinations of fertilizer application levels and irrigation intensities are shown, i.e., high fertilizer application combined with very high irrigation (airr), high irrigation (air2) and no irrigation (high); moderate fertilizer application combined with moderate irrigation (rirr), low irrigation (rir2) and no irrigation (moderate); low fertilizer application combined with no irrigation (low).

Table A.6

Land management on cropland in the Seewinkel region. Variabilities (i.e., coefficients of variation from the 30 bootstrapped realizations of the stochastic climate scenarios) for combinations of fertilizer application levels and irrigation intensities by λ levels (€/m³) and the three stochastic climate scenarios.

Management	high	moderate	low	airr	air2	rirr	rir2
λ	DRY						
0.7	0.034	0.003	0.000	NA	NA	0.038	0.019
0.6	0.034	0.003	0.000	NA	NA	0.039	0.018
0.5	0.034	0.003	0.000	NA	NA	0.022	0.012
0.4	0.033	0.003	0.000	NA	NA	0.006	0.005
0.3	0.031	0.004	0.001	NA	3.974	0.003	0.003
0.2	0.034	0.006	0.001	NA	0.021	0.001	0.009
0.1	0.037	0.034	0.008	0.021	0.002	0.001	0.035
0.0	NA	NA	6.058	0.002	0.001	0.003	1.819
λ	SIMILAR						
0.7	0.016	0.001	0.001	NA	NA	0.021	0.013
0.6	0.016	0.001	0.001	NA	NA	0.021	0.013
0.5	0.016	0.001	0.001	NA	NA	0.020	0.012
0.4	0.016	0.001	0.001	NA	NA	0.014	0.008

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Table A.6 (continued)

Management	high	moderate	low	airr	air2	rirr	rir2
0.3	0.018	0.001	0.001	NA	NA	0.007	0.006
0.2	0.022	0.002	0.001	NA	0.055	0.003	0.007
0.1	0.024	0.005	0.004	0.778	0.004	0.002	0.018
0.0	0.146	0.054	0.018	0.006	0.001	0.003	0.098
λ	WET						
0.7	0.006	0.001	0.001	NA	NA	0.092	0.025
0.6	0.006	0.001	0.001	NA	NA	0.092	0.025
0.5	0.006	0.001	0.001	NA	NA	0.091	0.022
0.4	0.007	0.001	0.002	NA	NA	0.061	0.018
0.3	0.009	0.001	0.002	NA	0.417	0.025	0.014
0.2	0.011	0.001	0.003	NA	0.164	0.010	0.014
0.1	0.012	0.002	0.005	NA	0.008	0.004	0.025
0.0	0.034	0.012	0.013	0.007	0.002	0.003	0.040

Note: Combinations of fertilizer application levels and irrigation intensities are shown, i.e., high fertilizer application combined with very high irrigation (airr), high irrigation (air2) and no irrigation (high); moderate fertilizer application combined with moderate irrigation (rirr), low irrigation (rir2) and no irrigation (moderate); low fertilizer application combined with no irrigation (low).

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